

FLIPPED CLASSROOM IN LEARNING GRADE 7 MATHEMATICS USING CROSS-OVER DESIGN: BASIS FOR INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study “Flipped Classroom in Learning Grade 7 Mathematics using Cross-Over Design: Basis for Instructional Material Development” aimed to determine the effectiveness of the Flipped Classroom Method in teaching mathematics to Grade 7 students at Leuteboro National High School during the school year 2024–2025, using a cross-over research design. A total of forty (40) Grade 7 students were selected through stratified random sampling and divided into two groups: control and experimental. Each group underwent both instructional methods across two phases, separated by a two-week washout period. Researcher-made pretests and posttests were used to assess academic performance before and after the application of each method, with statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, normality test, and paired t-test. Findings revealed that both instructional strategies led to improvements in students’ performance; however, the Flipped Classroom Method resulted in a higher increase in posttest scores, suggesting greater effectiveness in enhancing conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills. Analysis also showed that treatment effects were statistically significant, while period and carryover effects were negligible, affirming the validity of the cross-over design. The study concludes that the Flipped Classroom Method is a more effective approach to teaching mathematics among Grade 7 students and recommends the development and integration of instructional materials grounded in this method to promote active learning, deeper comprehension, and improved academic outcomes.

Keywords: *Flipped Classroom Method, Conventional Teaching Method, Cross-Over Design*

INTRODUCTION

Real-life problems can be solved by exploring numbers and pattern. Mathematics can turn difficult concepts to useful solutions by using logical reasoning and arithmetic.

Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2022, revealed that Filipino students is included in the world's weakest in mathematics, there was no improvement in country's performance based on its scores from 353 in 2018 to 355 in 2022 (Chi, 2023). Moreover, the capability of Filipino in mathematics is named as "level 2 proficiency" because only 16% of students in the Philippines achieved at least the starting point.

Moreover, the outcome of 2018 National Achievement Test for Grade 10 students in the Philippines indicated that their performance in Mathematics falls within the "low proficiency" range. Data revealed that the mean score in Mathematics is declining with more than 80% at low or zero proficiency.

A level of low mastery was also observed in the Grade 7 participants in mathematics at Leuteboro National High School. This is based on the summative Mean Percentage Score (MPS) in the school year 2023-2024. The mean percentage score of the students was 62% and below the satisfactory level of 75. This implies that students were experiencing difficulty in solving problems in mathematics. The situation has led to a decrease in math learning, remediation was needed to proceed to new lessons (Torres, 2021).

In response to this alarming situation, DepEd introduced MATATAG Curriculum. This curriculum was implemented under Republic Act No. 11476, which emphasizes foundational skills in mathematics. According to DepEd Order number 010, s. 2024, teachers should adapt their pedagogical methods and strategies to keep learners engaged while continuously adjusting teaching practices aligned to core instructional principles outlined in the MATATAG Curriculum.

In this study, the flipped classroom was a method in which lessons learned at home and teachers prepared recorded videos for students to access before class, and activities were done at school. Students will have enough time to finish all the assessments and activities.

In his study, Hava (2020) defined flipped classroom as a delivered online resource. He outlined that this method enhanced the engagement of the students more than conventional learning. Furthermore, a limitation of this study was the participation in the class discussion was not measured before the application was processed. The current study has addressed this limitation. The present study employed a crossover research design with pretest and posttest. One suggestion in this research was the teacher should record the video using his own voice, as this could provide a better understanding of the students because they recognize the voice. This research used lesson recorded by the teacher, ensuring an improve comprehension of the lesson.

With this, the researcher is conducted this study to help Grade 7 participants of Leuteboro National High School address the difficulty in Mathematics and gained a better understanding of sets and integers. The researcher assumed that flipped classroom method would lead to the mastery of the mathematics' core competencies.

The aforementioned discussions have increased the interest of the researcher's determination to study deeply the effectiveness of the flipped classroom method.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of performance of control group participants before using Conventional Teaching Method?
2. What is the level of performance of experimental group participants before using Flipped Classroom Method?
3. What is the level of performance of control group participants after using Conventional Teaching Method?
4. What is the level of performance of experimental group participants after using Flipped Classroom Method?
5. How do the pretest and posttest results of participants in control group differ?
6. How do the pretest and posttest results of participants in experimental group differ?
7. How does the pretest level of performance differ between participants of control group in terms of:
 - a. treatment effect,
 - b. period effect, and
 - c. carryover effect?
8. How does the posttest level of performance differ between participants of control group and experimental group in terms of:
 - a. treatment effect,
 - b. period effect, and
 - c. carryover effect?
9. Based on the findings of the study, what instructional material may be developed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental utilizing crossover method, involving both experimental and control groups. The research aimed to determine the effectiveness of the Flipped Classroom Method as developed instructional material in teaching selected mathematics topics to Grade 7 students at Leuteboro National High School. A total of forty (40) Grade 7 students participated in the study and were equally divided into two groups of twenty (20) each. The selection of participants was based on their academic performance levels: Advanced, Proficient, Approaching Proficiency, and Developing, following the descriptors and grading scale from DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015. This ensured that both groups had comparable average scores and standard deviations, reducing selection bias and enhancing the internal validity of the study.

The instructional intervention was conducted in two phases, separated by a two-week washout period to reduce potential carryover effects. Before the first phase of instruction, a researcher-made pretest was administered to both groups to assess their baseline understanding. In Phase 1, one group was taught using the Conventional Teaching Method while the other received instruction through the Flipped Classroom Method. Both groups studied the topic of sets, which included describing and illustrating sets and subsets, as well as performing union and intersection operations. Following instruction, a posttest was given to both groups to evaluate their performance.

After a two-week break, Phase 2 commenced with the groups switching instructional strategies. The group that initially received conventional instruction was now taught using the Flipped Classroom Method, while the other group reverted to the Conventional Teaching Method. This phase focused on the topic of integers, particularly the four fundamental operations. A second posttest was administered after this phase to measure learning gains. This crossover design allowed each group to experience both instructional methods, helping control for individual differences and other confounding variables, and ensuring that observed differences in performance could be attributed to the teaching method.

The primary instrument used for data collection was a researcher-made test consisting of twenty (20) items per phase. These test items were designed in alignment with the Grade 7 mathematics competencies outlined for the third quarter, specifically targeting the topics of sets and integers. To ensure the validity of the instrument, it underwent a content validation process conducted by a panel of three Master Teachers in Mathematics. These experts were from Nabuslot National High School, Leuteboro National High School, and Bayuin National High School, all within the Schools Division of Oriental Mindoro. Each validator held a Master of Arts in Mathematics Education and had more than five years of teaching experience. Their feedback and suggestions were incorporated into the final version of the tests.

Data collected from the pretests and posttests were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and normality tests were used to summarize the data. To determine whether there were significant differences in student performance between and within groups across the two instructional phases, a paired t-test was employed. This combination of quantitative methods enabled a comprehensive analysis of the instructional impact of the Flipped Classroom Method in comparison to the Conventional Teaching Method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of Performance of Control Group Participants Before Using Conventional Teaching Method

Scores	Phase 1		Phase 2		Description
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
17 – 20	0	0.00	0	0.00	Very High
13 – 16	0	0.00	1	5.00	High
9 – 12	4	20.00	4	20.00	Average
5 – 8	15	75.00	9	45.00	Low
0 – 4	1	5.00	6	30.00	Very Low
TOTAL	20	100.00	20	100.00	
	Mean: 5.80		Mean: 6.65		
	Description: Low		Description: Low		

In phase 1, the mean value of control group before conventional teaching method was 5.80, described as low. The results implied that the control group participants had prior but insufficient knowledge of sets. The procedures involved were complex, making it hard for them to determine the correct answers. Thus, many participants had a hard time answering the test. Mean score in phase 2 was 6.65, also described as low. The findings suggested that the control group participants had inadequate knowledge of integers. They demonstrated a weak understanding of how integers work and might have been unsure about positive and negative numbers.

The inadequate knowledge of the students regarding Mathematics concepts such as sets and integers was confirmed by Chikeme et al. (2024). They outlined the lack of foundational knowledge of the mathematical concepts harms the abilities of the student to engage with more problem-solving tasks.

2. Level of Performance of Experimental Group Participants Before Using Flipped Classroom Method

Scores	Phase 1		Phase 2		Description
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
17 – 20	0	0.00	0	0.00	Very High
13 – 16	0	0.00	2	10.00	High
9 – 12	6	30.00	4	20.00	Average
5 – 8	12	60.00	9	45.00	Low
0 - 4	2	10.00	5	25.00	Very Low
TOTAL	20	100.00	20	100.00	
	Mean: 6.15		Mean: 6.80		
	Description: Low		Description: Low		

Average score of the experimental group in phase 1 was 6.15, described as low. The results were explained by the fact that students' test scores were the same as to control group before conventional teaching method was implemented. The same low results were because to their limited knowledge of sets. According to Jones (2020), the

fact that the teacher has not discussed the topic yet, the findings are expected to be very low since they do not have a foundation for the topic.

In phase 2, mean value was 6.80, also described as low. The result illustrated their little prior knowledge and understanding regarding the concepts in sets and integers. Also, participants were unable to use their intellect to solve complex problems in the test. Shao (2021) asserted that the result was anticipated to be at a low level since they lacked foundational understanding of the topic which affected their ability to answer complex questions in the test.

3. Level of Performance of Control Group Participants After Using Conventional Teaching Method

Scores	Phase 1		Phase 2		Description
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
17 – 20	0	0.00	1	5.00	Very High
13 – 16	7	35.00	5	25.00	High
9 – 12	11	55.00	9	45.00	Average
5 – 8	2	10.00	5	25.00	Low
0 – 4	0	0.00	0	0.00	Very Low
TOTAL	20	100.00	20	100.00	
	Mean: 11.50		Mean: 11.95		
	Description: Average		Description: Average		

In phase 1, the control group participants had an average score of 11.50, described as average, following the conventional teaching method. The participants showed improved results in the test, and demonstrated a basic understanding of sets, as shown by their ability to answer the test correctly even the complex problems. In phase 2, mean value was 11.95, also described as average. This revealed that after employing a conventional teaching method, participants showed improved results in the test, and demonstrated a basic understanding of sets, as shown by their ability to answer the test correctly even the complex problems.

This is aligned to the findings of Baxter and King (2022) who highlighted that any strategy could be effective if the pupils were motivated to learn. When learners were genuinely interested, even the most complex or demanding strategies can succeed.

4. Level Performance of Experimental Group Participants After Using Flipped Classroom Method

Scores	Phase 1		Phase 2		Description
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
17 – 20	3	15.00	2	10.00	Very High
13 – 16	8	40.00	10	50.00	High
9 – 12	9	45.00	7	35.00	Average
5 – 8	0	0.00	1	5.00	Low
0 – 4	0	0.00	0	0.00	Very Low
TOTAL	20	100.00	20	100.00	
	Mean: 14.05		Mean: 13.90		
	Description: High		Description: High		

The mean score of the experimental group in phase 1 was 14.05, described as high. When students were taught using flipped classroom method, the performance improved from low to high. This suggested that the students gained understanding of sets and were able to apply their knowledge by correctly answering the questions. In phase 2, the mean value was 13.90, also described as high. This conveyed that the participants' level of academic performance increased after employing the method. This indicated that participants demonstrated a clear understanding of fundamental concepts of integers.

This is reinforced by Hew et al. (2021) who stated that after being exposed to intervention, students improved their understanding. Through intervention, the students' skills and abilities were developed, and their misconceptions about integers were corrected.

5. Difference between Pretest and Posttest Performance of Participants in Control Group Using Conventional Teaching Method

	Compared Variables	N	Mean	Mean Difference	SD	Computed t-value	Critical value	df	Result
Phase 1	Pretest	20	5.80	5.70	2.25	11.33	2.09	19	Significant
	Posttest	20	11.50						
Phase 2	Pretest	20	6.65	5.30	1.42	16.72	2.09	19	Significant
	Posttest	20	11.50						

For phase 1, the computed t-value of 11.33 was more than the critical value of 2.09 at the 0.05 level of significance. For phase 2, calculated t-value of 16.72 went beyond the critical t-value of 2.09 at the 0.05 level of significance. There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performance of the participants in the control group.

This implied conventional teaching method was effective in improving students' understanding of sets and integers. It suggested that conventional instruction helped

students grasp the fundamental concepts and apply them accurately. Smith and Jones (2021) asserted that a teacher's physical presence in the classroom allows them to engage with students one-on-one. This leads to better performance of students because they are more focus during class discussions.

6. Difference between Pretest and Posttest of the Participants in Experimental Group Using Flipped Classroom Method

	Compared Variables	N	Mean	Mean Difference	SD	Computed t-value	Critical value	df	Result
Phase 1	Pretest	20	6.15						
	Posttest	20	14.05	7.90	2.36	14.97	2.09	19	Significant
Phase	Pretest	20	6.80						
	Posttest	20	13.90	7.10	1.37	23.13	2.09	19	Significant

For Phase 1, the observed t-value of 14.97 surpassed the critical value of 2.09 at the 0.05 level of significance. The computed t-value of 23.14 exceeded the critical t-value of 2.09 at the 0.05 level of significance. There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performance of the participants in the experimental group.

Outcome suggested that Grade 7 participants performed better in solving problems involving sets and integers when flipped classroom method was employed. It indicated innovations in teaching methods had a remarkable effect on the performance of the students, as they promoted deeper understanding, increased engagement, and more effective learning outcomes. Abah (2020) added that innovative pedagogies nurture critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving abilities—attributes vital for navigating contemporary challenges and opportunities.

7. Difference between Performances of Participants of Control and Experimental Group in Pretest Using Conventional Teaching Method and Flipped Classroom Method

7a. Treatment Effect

Compared Groups	N	Parameter Estimate	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	t-Critical value	df	Result
Conventional Teaching Method	40	6.23					
Flipped Classroom Method	40	6.48	0.25	0.57	2.02	39	Not Significant

The calculated t-value of 0.57 did not surpass the critical value of 2.02 using 39

degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. There is no significant difference in the treatment effect on the pretest performance between the participants in the control and experimental groups.

Result showed that pre-test is a valuable source of prior knowledge of students' initial level of understanding of the concepts of sets and integers. This is supported by Noreen et al. (2021), who suggest that educational institutions should have a concrete plan for devising strategies to make learning adaptable in times of crisis. It can then be inferred the teachers need to be flexible in teaching delivery, incorporating various appropriate strategies to help students learn, especially in Mathematics.

7b. Period Effect

Compared Groups	N	Parameter Estimate	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Critical value	df	Result
Period 1	40	5.98	0.75	1.36	2.02	39	Not Significant
Period 2	40	6.73					

The computed t-value of 1.36 failed to exceed the critical value of 2.02, using 39 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. There is no significant difference in the period effect in the pretest performance between the participants in the control and experimental groups. Findings highlighted that score did not change over time for the treatment effect. This indicated that scores in the pretest of Grade 7 participants were not modified in subsequent periods/phases.

The result validated the findings by Lim and In (2021), who outlined that when comparing values obtained from different periods, there should have been no difference if the period effect was absent. This indicated that the timing of the intervention did not affect the outcome.

7c. Carryover Effect

Compared Groups	N	Parameter Estimate	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Critical value	df	Result
Sequence 1	20	6.15	0.65	0.76	2.02	19	Not Significant
Sequence 2	20	6.80					

The observed t-value of 0.76 remained below under the critical value of 2.09 using 19 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. There is no significant difference in the carryover effect in the pretest performance between the participants in the control and experimental groups. This implies that some contributory factors included the sufficient time or washout period allocated to both groups before proceeding to the next sequence, as well as the fact that participants' score was based solely on what they already knew about the topics.

The results conformed to the conclusion stated by Heesen (2020), who outlined that in the absence of carryover effects, a compelling balance emerged between enhancing statistical power and detecting meaningful differences between the interventions.

8. Difference between Performances of Participants on Control and Experimental Groups in Posttest Using Conventional Teaching and Flipped Classroom Methods

8a. Treatment Effect

Compared Groups	N	Parameter Estimate	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Critical value	df	Result
Conventional Teaching Method	40	11.73					
Flipped Classroom Method	40	13.98	2.25	4.28	2.02	39	Significant

The calculated t-value of 4.28 was greater than the critical value of 2.02 using 39 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. There is a significant difference in the treatment effect in the posttest performance between the participants in the control and experimental groups. The findings inferred that Grade 7 participants were able to answer the test involving sets and integers when both methods were used. This suggested that both methods contributed positively to the analytical skills of the students.

Outcome showed that after the conventional teaching method was implemented, the obtained mean value was 11.28, while the gained mean score was 13.98 after the flipped classroom method was applied. This revealed that the flipped classroom method was more efficient in improving the academic performance of the students compared to the conventional teaching method.

In addition, results were parallel to what was stated by Thai et al. (2017). They outlined that this method enhanced quality of learning because students were more likely to prepare beforehand in flipped classrooms than in conventional teaching classes.

8b. Period Effect

Compared Groups	N	Parameter Estimate	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Critical value	df	Result
Period 1	40	12.78					
Period 2	40	12.93	0.15	0.25	2.02	39	Not Significant

The observed t-value of 0.25 stayed under the critical value of 2.02 using 39 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. There is no significant difference in

the period effect in the posttest performance between the participants in the control and experimental groups. Results conveyed that the participants' scores remained consistent over time, indicating that the treatment effect was stable and not influenced by the passage of time. This suggested that whether the participants received the treatment earlier or later, their performance remained relatively the same. This indicated that the treatment effect was steady and not influenced by when it was administered.

The results were consistent with the findings of Fannakhosrow (2021). They concluded that if the washout period was too long, dropout rates might rise, making crossover studies difficult or impossible. However, if there was no period effect, the timing between treatments unable to influence the results, helping maintain the reliability of the study despite the length of the washout period.

8c. Carryover Effect

Compared Groups	N	Parameter Estimate	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Critical value	df	Result
Sequence 1	20	14.05	0.15	0.17	2.09	19	Not Significant
Sequence 2	20	13.90					

The computed t-value of 0.17 was less than the critical value of 2.09 using 19 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. There is no significant difference in the carryover effect in the posttest performance between the participants in the control and experimental groups. The findings corresponded with the discussion of Sparrow et al. (2023), who stressed that with carryover effect set to 0, both the standard crossover t-test and the mixed model with no carryover term exhibit no bias, correct coverage, and correct type I error.

9. Proposed Instructional Material Development

As a part of the proposed instructional materials for this study, the researcher developed a series of four educational video tutorials aligned with the Grade 7 Mathematics curriculum for the third quarter. The topics were presented in the following sequence: (1) Sets and Kinds of Sets, (2) Union and Intersection of Sets, (3) Addition and Subtraction of Integers, and (4) Multiplication and Division of Integers. Each video followed a structured format: a review of prior knowledge, contextual introduction, clear discussion of new concepts with examples, guided practice, generalization and evaluation. The videos utilized visual aids and real-life contexts to promote student engagement and understanding. Designed for home-based learning in a flipped classroom setup, these materials aimed to strengthen learners' mastery of key mathematical concepts.

TOPIC	URL:	QR CODE
Sets and Kinds of Sets	https://youtu.be/AUgc_YOPR4Y	

TOPIC	URL:	QR CODE
Union and Intersection of Sets with Venn Diagrams	https://youtu.be/vHrxuz-IC7Y	

TOPIC	URL	QR CODE
Addition and Subtraction of Integers	https://youtu.be/WaUTxmOwFvY	

TOPIC	URL:	QR CODE
Multiplication and Division of Integers	https://youtu.be/MUcqxNRE0rU	

Conclusions

The findings revealed that both conventional and flipped classroom methods improved students' academic performance in mathematics. Also, flipped classroom method resulted in higher posttest scores than the conventional teaching method. Students using the flipped classroom method showed an improve understanding of mathematical concepts, especially sets and integers. In addition, the flipped classroom method was more effective in enhancing students' problem-solving skills in mathematics. Improvement in solving problems on sets and integers was observed in Grade 7

participants after being taught through the conventional teaching method. However, compared to the conventional teaching method, Grade 7 participants using the flipped classroom method demonstrated better performance in solving problems on sets and integers. Moreover, instruction using both conventional teaching methods and flipped classroom method resulted in equally weak performance in pretest in solving problems on sets and integers. However, participants' scores on each method differ in each phase, and they performed similarly on both sequences. Furthermore, Grade 7 participants showed improvement in the posttest when solving problems on sets and integers after using both the conventional teaching method and flipped classroom method. Furthermore, following treatment effect, they demonstrated a significantly greater performance on the implementation of flipped classroom method. After period effect, participants' scores remained consistent over time concerning the treatment effect. Additionally, Grade 7 participants performed similarly across both sequences, indicating that the results were not influenced by the carryover effect.

Recommendations

Taking into account the findings and conclusions of this research, the following recommendations are suggested. Teachers may use the Flipped Classroom Method in teaching mathematics to improve student performance. Schools may develop video-based instructional materials to support flipped classroom implementation, while conventional teaching methods may still be utilized alongside the flipped classroom approach to cater to diverse learners. It is also recommended that teachers be trained to efficiently create and deliver flipped classroom content. School administrators may support the use of flipped classroom strategies to encourage student engagement. Furthermore, instructional materials may be enhanced and developed based on the successful output of this study. Future researchers may explore the application of the flipped classroom method to other mathematics topics or subjects. The crossover design may be used in future research to ensure a reliable comparison of teaching methods, and researchers may consider extending the washout period or using larger samples when applying crossover designs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm that the study titled *Flipped Classroom in Learning Grade 7 Mathematics Using Cross-Over Design: Basis for Instructional Material Development* was conducted in accordance with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and their guardians, and respondents were free to withdraw at any time. Anonymity and confidentiality were ensured, and data privacy protocols were strictly followed. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the study. The authors declare no conflict of interest, ensured that plagiarism was avoided, and maintained objectivity in interpreting the findings. The results were used solely for research purposes, and any use of artificial intelligence was fully disclosed.

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REFERENCES

- Abah, J. (2020). An Appeal in the Case involving Conventional Teaching: Emphasizing the Transformation to Enhanced Conventional Teaching in Mathematics Education. *Village Math Educational Review*, 1(1), 1–10. <https://villagemath.net/journals/ver/v1i1/abah>
- Baxter, T., & King, L. (2020). Rethinking traditional instruction: Challenges for the 21st century. *Journal of Pedagogical Innovation*, 29(2), 55–78. <https://doi.org/10.18174/572267>
- Chi, C. (2023, December 9). Philippines still lags behind world in math, reading and science — PISA 2022. *Philstar.com*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/12/06/2316732/philippines-still-lags-behind-world-math-reading-and-science-pisa-2022>
- Chikeme, P. C., Ihudiebube-Splendor, C. N., Ogbonnaya, N. P., Mbadugha, C. J., & Elodi, L. O. (2024). Flipped classroom model versus conventional teaching method: effects on nursing students' self-directed learning readiness in a research methodology course. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 47. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2024.47.70.38359>
- Department of Education. (2019). 2018 National Achievement Test (NAT) 6, 10 & 12 results and analysis. Department of Education Regional Office II. <https://region2.deped.gov.ph/urm-s-20192018-national-achievement-test-nat-610-12-results-and-analysis/>
- Fannakhosrow, M., Nourabadi, S., Huy, D. T. N., Trung, N. D., & Tashtoush, M. A. (2022). A Comparative Study of Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-Based and Conventional Methods of Instruction on Learners' Academic Enthusiasm for L2 Learning. *Education Research International*, 2022, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5478088>
- Hava, K. (2020). The effects of the flipped classroom on deep learning strategies and engagement at the undergraduate level. *Participatory Educational Research*, 8(1), 379–394. <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.21.22.8.1>
- Heesen, P. (2020, September 7). Crossover trials: what are they and what are their advantages and limitations? *Students 4 Best Evidence*. <https://s4be.cochrane.org/blog/2020/09/07/crossover-trials-what-are-they-and-what-are-their-advantages-and-limitations/>
- Hew, K. F., Bai, S., Dawson, P., & Lo, C. K. (2021). Meta-analyses of flipped classroom studies: A review of methodology. *Educational Research Review*, 33, 100393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2021.100393>
- Jones, M. (2020). Student voice to improve schools: Perspectives from students, teachers and leaders in 'perfect' conditions. *Improving Schools*, 24(3), 233–244. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1365480219901064>

- Lim, C.-Y., & In, J. (2021). Considerations for Crossover Design in Clinical Study. *Korean Journal of Anesthesiology*, 74(4), 293–299. <https://doi.org/10.4097/kja.21165>
- Noreen, R., & Rana, A. M. (2021). Activity-Based Teaching versus Traditional Method of Teaching in Mathematics at Elementary Level. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 4(2), 145–159. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1229426>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). *PISA 2022 results (Volume I): The state of learning and equity in education*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/53f23881>
- Shao, M., & Liu, X. (2021). Impact of the Flipped Classroom on Students' Learning Performance via Meta-Analysis. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 09(09), 82–109. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2021.99007>
- Smith, J. A., & Johnson, L. B. (2021). The impact of digital learning on academic performance. *Educational Research Journal*, 45(2), 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.58812/wsis.v1i6.89>
- Sparrow, D., DeMolles, D., Ornella Dubaz, Durso, R., & Rosner, B. (2023). Design issues in crossover trials involving patients with Parkinson's disease. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2023.1197281>
- Thai, N. T. T., De Wever, B., & Valcke, M. (2017). The impact of a flipped classroom design on learning performance in higher education: Looking for the best “blend” of lectures and guiding questions with feedback. *Computers & Education*, 107, 113–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2017.01.00>
- Torres, R. C. (2021). Addressing the Learning Gaps in the Distance Learning Modalities. <http://ijeais.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/6/abs/IJAAR210611.html>